

Bocage agroforestry in Normandy

With approximately 171,000 km of hedgerows, Normandy is the third most bocage-rich region in France. The average density of Norman hedgerows (estimated at 57 m ha⁻¹) is well above the national average (28 m ha⁻¹). The region is characterized by a heterogeneous distribution of hedgerow lengths across departments, a landscape legacy reflecting the evolution of agricultural practices.

CARBON SEQUESTRATION

Thanks to photosynthesis, the woody perennial hedgerow captures atmospheric carbon, storing it in its aboveground and root biomass. In Normandy, the median sequestration potential in harvested aboveground biomass is estimated at 9.6 tCO₂-eq km⁻¹ year⁻¹. It is particularly efficient in the region: hedgerow trees grow on average 1.6 times faster than deciduous forests, benefiting rich and well-drained agricultural soils, as well as better access to light resources. Organic carbon stocks are 14% higher in the immediate vicinity of hedgerows (up to 2 m) compared with arable fields, with an average additional storage of 0.69 t C 100 m⁻¹. Coppiced hedgerows, which account for three quarters of the regional hedgerow network, show the highest productivity (7.4 m³ km⁻¹ year⁻¹) and thus contribute to a dynamic carbon flux. Intra-plot agroforestry allows for additional storage of +207 kg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, offering a transferable solution to improve the resilience of agricultural systems

Normandy Bocage © Ver de Terre Production

CLIMATE RESILIENCE

In the face of a projected temperature increase of +3.6°C by 2100 in Normandy under the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) 8.5 scenario, bocage management must anticipate these changes to ensure its long-term viability. These projections translate into 42 additional hot days and 23 fewer frost days. The repeated occurrence of drought and heatwave episodes over several years, more than isolated extreme events, may lead to the gradual decline of certain species, such as beech. Species selection therefore becomes strategic: historically present but sometimes forgotten species such as lime (linden), wild cherry or chestnut, deserve to be replanted, as they are better adapted to the new climatic conditions.

KEYWORDS

bocage, agroforestry, carbon sequestration, climate resilience, normandy.

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